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Alchemy and Sacred Geography in the Mediaeval Deccan*

ARION ROŞU

*Paṇḍitānām Niddodi-Rāmacandra-
Bhaṭṭānām saptatitame janmadināvasare.*

In the course of my research on the history of Rasaśāstra, I learned, in the early 1980's, from a colleague who had visited the temples of Alampur, that the iconography of this Śaivite site as well as local traditions pointed to the former presence of alchemists in this region of the Deccan. In order to verify the grounds for this information, I proceeded with research that was as much philological and historical as it was archaeological and anthropological. I now wish to present the results of this interdisciplinary investigation, undertaken in libraries as well as in the field in Andhra Pradesh, in the sacred area of Śrīśailam, of which Alampur and other Śaivite sites are the constitutive parts.

The uncertainties regarding the origins of Indian alchemy and the development of its practices, together with the late appearance of its post-Gupta literature, cast a veil of obscurity over historical knowledge in this field. For this reason the Indologist should exploit any cultural vein that might yield material on the sketchy history of Rasaśāstra. From this point of view the legends concerning the holy place of Śrīśailam/Śrīparvata and the traditional gateway temples located at its cardinal points — especially Alampur to the west — are worth studying because of their abundant references to alchemy.

Śrīśailam is located at the high point of the Nallamalai Hills, to the south of the Kṛṣṇā River. According to a tradition corroborated by epigraphic evidence, the principal approaches to this nearly inaccessible holy place passed through four gateways, which faced the four cardinal directions. These were Tripurāntakam to the east, Siddhavattam to the south, Alampur to the west, and Umāmaheśvaram to the north. Since the time of the Rāṣtrakūṭas (757—973) inscriptions mention Śrīśailam as having four main gateways (*dvāra*).

It is Śaivism that provides the framework for the religious links that join these four main gateways to the pilgrimage centre of Śrīśailam. The sacred area defined within these limits is an apparent representation of the *mahāsadāśivatattva*, which is itself manifested in Śiva's five forms. The god Mallikāṛjuna of Śrīśailam itself thus corresponds to Īśāna, while the gateways to Śrīśailam are marked by *mukhalingakṣetras* which correspond to Śiva's four other forms: these are Tatpuruṣa to the east (Tripurāntakam), Aghora to the south (Siddhavattam), Sadyojāta to the west (Alampur) and Vāmadeva to the north (Umāmaheśvaram).

Śrīśailam, the centre of Śaivism in the Deccan, has been mentioned in both Sanskrit and Dravidian literatures since the first centuries of the Christian era. Archaeological remains testify to the great antiquity of Śaivite devotion in the lower Kṛṣṇā valley, which

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separates the Deccan to the north from the peninsular plains to the south.¹ The beginning of work on the Śrīśailam Dam has given a new impulse to archaeological research here over the past years.² This Hydroelectric Project has led to the systematic exploration of archaeological sites as well as to salvage operations (principally the transplant of several monuments threatened by the waters of an artificial reservoir into the Mahbubnagar and Kurnool Districts of Andhra Pradesh).³

Located on the Nallamalai Range, Śrīśailam is a site surrounded on all sides by forest. The geological grandeur of this plateau, already described in ancient accounts of the sacred place, still impresses the modern traveller. In its chapter entitled *Śrīśailopā-khyāna*, the *Padma-Purāna* refers to the area's rich plant life and natural beauty, both of which were favourable to the spiritual exercises of ascetics there. The magnificence of the site is also evoked in the more prosaic description given of Śrīśailam in Āndhra village registers, the famous *kaifiyats* of the MacKenzie Collection. These Telugu administrative records apart from their information on the wide variety of fauna thriving in the area's dense forests, also note the activities of the herbalists of the Śrīśailam region, whose medicinal plants are used both in the preparation of drugs and in alchemical operations (*rasavāda*).⁴

Such natural conditions favour the therapeutic and chemical activities sometimes referred to in pilgrimage literature. Texts in this popular genre naively invite the Indian authorities to encourage a study of the area's natural resources. Even today, there is a number of *sādhus* at Śrīśalam who prepare plant- and mineral-based remedies, and people still love to tell the tale of the rapid healing of a worker on the Śrīśailam Project whose wound was treated with such preparations. These local healers, who also know the location of springs of pure water, which quench all thirst, are supposed to prepare their medicines by the *puṭa* method of heating, traditional to Āyurveda and Rasaśāstra. Similarly, at Alampur, the western gateway to Śrīśailam, Gadiyarama Ramakrishna Sarma, a local pandit who is especially interested in the region's alchemical tradition, asserts that it is still possible to prepare, with local herbs, the medicines formerly prescribed by the *siddhas* in the alchemical texts (*Ānandakanda*, *Rasaratnākara*).

In the context of itinerant devotion, the clockwise circumambulation (*pradakṣiṇa*) of the Mallikārjuna temple at Śrīśailam is an act of infinite merit (*anantapuṇya*), while in Āndhra, this *tīrtha* represents the sacred centre towards which the devotee of Śiva orients himself in order to formulate the ritual intention (*saṅkalpa*) prior to his daily worship. Among the earliest Sanskrit sources to refer to Śrīśailam are Subandhu's

¹ See V. Anuradha, *Temples at Śrīśailam. An Art Historical Study*. Ph.D. - thesis in the Department of History and Archaeology, Nagarjuna University (Nagarjuna Nagar, Andhra Pradesh) 1988. This doctoral dissertation is the most complete monograph written on the subject since the first description of Śrīśailam by Colin MacKenzie (*Asiatic Researches 1798*). However, before publication this dissertation needs attentive revision.

² See B. Dagens, *Entre Alampur et Śrīśailam. Recherches archéologiques en Andhra Pradesh*, Pondichéry 1984. Cf. *An Encyclopaedia of Indian Archaeology* edited by A. Ghosh II, New Delhi 1989, 420-422: Śrīśailam Project submersible area.

³ See e.g. I.K. Sarma, 'Alampur Temples. Rare Evidences on Constructional Modes and Consecrational Rites', *Personality in Indian Archaeology. Essays in Honour of B.K. Thapar* (in press).

⁴ P. Sitapati, *Srisailam Temple Kaifiyat, I [English Summary]*, Hyderabad 1981, 22.

Vāsavadattā, a seventh century romance, and the *Padma-Purāṇa*, which offers the hope of deliverance (*mukti*) to those who have seen the holy mountain. According to legend, Śrīśailam, besides being visited by Śaṅkara, was a site at which Nāgārjuna set up an alchemical laboratory (*Rasaratnākara*), and the place where Vyāsa wrote the *Śrīśaila-khaṇḍa*.

The alchemical activities associated with this Śaivite site, as described in the *Rasa-śāstra* texts and in the pilgrimage literature, correspond to the manifold functions of the temple in India, where sanctuaries, besides being religious centres, are also pivots of social, cultural and economic activity.

We find here and there in the Sanskrit literary sources references to various tantric trends that grew out of the Kāpālīka presence at Śrīśailam. Inscriptions dating from the seventh century onwards indicate that Śaivism was principally represented in this holy place by the Kālāmukha school (related in its doctrines to the Pāśupatas), which was predominant in Āndhra from the 9th to 12th centuries, prior to the rise of the Viraśaivas in the 13th and 14th centuries. In this period, the authority of the religious superiors of Śrīśailam extended over all the Śaivite temples of both Karṇāṭaka and Āndhra.

Śrīśailam is reputed to be a *siddhikṣetra*, an ideal place for yogins, as well as for magicians and those contemplatives known as *siddhas*, whose doctrine is an element of tantrism. Whether legendary or real, these eminent beings are considered to have attained spiritual perfection or to have come to possess wondrous powers of both a spiritual and material nature (the art of healing, techniques of rejuvenation, alchemical operations, etc.). A number of temples in the Śrīśailam area are consecrated to Śiva Siddheśvara, the lord of the "perfected ones". According to certain archaeologists, these sanctuaries may have been founded by *siddha* ascetics who were practitioners of alchemy (*rasavāda*). Datable to the seventh century on the basis of both their architecture and inscriptions, these temples likely belong to the same period as that in which the *siddha* movement originated in the region.

In the eighth century, Bhavabhūti's *Mālatīmādhava* evokes a Kāpālīka centre at Śrīśailam, out of which came such tantrics as the skull-bearing Aghoraghaṇṭa, who haunted cremation grounds in order to propitiate the goddess Cāmuṇḍā with terrible forms of worship. A difficult episode in the life of Śaṅkarācārya is also said to have occurred in or near Śrīśailam, where he was nearly sacrificed by the evil Kāpālīka Ugra-Bhairava. One of the characters in Kṣemīśvara's drama called *Caṇḍakauśika* (10th or 11th century) is possessed of magical abilities, some of which seem to recall the wondrous powers known to Buddhist tantrism, such as elixirs of long life (*rasāyanas*) and the transmutation of base metals (*dhātuvāda*).

Several centuries after Bhavabhūti, the presence of *siddhas* and Kāpālīkas at Śrīśailam is confirmed in Kalhaṇa's *Rājatarāṅgiṇī*. This twelfth-century literary reference is reinforced by data found in the alchemical literature. At many points the *Rasārṇava*, which dates from the same period, cites procedures (*kramas*, *yogas*) employed by the Kāpālīka ascetics to tint mercury and other metals. The *Rasakāmadhenu*, a late text dating from the seventeenth century, contains references to these same processes, which are attributed to the Kāpālīkas.

From the *Mahābhārata* onwards, we encounter the names of Śrīparvata or Śrīśailam throughout Sanskrit literature as well as in a number of Prakrit and vernacular sources. However, it is the Purāṇic texts, and most notably the *Skanda-Purāṇa* and the literature attached to it, which contain the greatest wealth of references to this subject. This text

has come down to us in two recensions, the one published and the other unedited; as such, it remains impossible for us to define the relationship between what are actually two homonymous works. The printed editions of the *Skanda-Purāna* vary from the original composition of the text and include many independent documents (*māhātmyas*, *ākhyānas*, etc.), which are at times translated or adapted into vernacular languages.

There is still great confusion about the literature claiming allegiance to the *Skanda-Purāna*, including the *Śrīśailakhaṇḍa* and *Śrīśailamāhātmya*. The former text has recently been adapted into Telugu, on the basis of a number of Sanskrit manuscripts, a work intended to remedy the prior absence of a vernacular text glorifying this celebrated Śaiva *kṣetra* of the Deccan. Concerning particular pilgrimage sites, the *māhātmyas* or *sthala-purānas*, though of recent origin, seek to attach themselves to one or another ancient Purāna.

Like many Indian sovereigns, the princes of the Āndhra country gave constant support to Sanskrit literary production, down to the 14th-15th centuries, when the Reḍḍi kings began to favour literary creations in the language of the country. Relieved of the weight of Sanskrit domination, Telugu has become the vehicle for a vernacular literature that, while it reflects pan-Indian values, also bears the stamp of Āndhra culture, a culture marked in the mediaeval period by the *siddha* ideology of "perfected" beings renowned for their signal abilities in yoga (supernatural powers), alchemy (aurifaction) and medicine (techniques for good health and rejuvenation).

Spread over the whole of the subcontinent and beyond (Nepal, Tibet), the *siddha* cult, common to both Hindus and Buddhists, produced several lists that enumerate these superior beings, varying in number between five and eighty-four. Certain of these *siddhas*, such as Matsyendra and his disciple Gorakṣa, are names that are as greatly revered in the North as they are in South India. These belong to the group of the nine 'Protectors' (*nātha*), whose legends make up the subject matter of the poem entitled *Navanāthacaritra*, written in Telugu by Gaurana in the 14th or 15th century. This work was written at the request of the superior of one of the five Śaiva manasteries of Śrīśailam. This sacred site is in fact singled out in the Nātha or Siddha traditions as a place visited by their most renowned masters.

According to Gaurana, Nāgārjunanātha taught aurifaction (*siddhahemavāda*) to a disciple whom he called Ātreya; in an earlier portion of Gaurana's poem, however, this same individual is called Nāgārjuna Siddha. Dr. P.V. Parabrahma Sastry sees this as a corrupted reading, and suggests that Ātreya be replaced with *ātmīya*. Nāgārjuna would in fact have given his own (*ātmīya*) name to his disciple, who was thenceforth known as Nāgārjuna Siddha or Siddha Nāgārjuna. It was in any case this disciple who, initiated into alchemy, proceeded with an experiment of transmutation at Śrīśailam, by which he intended to transform the mountain into a heap of gold. This gold-maker's projected experiment was halted by the god Viṣṇu, who went so far as to take the ambitious alchemist's life. Here, the vernacular account overlaps with Sanskrit literature, which also knows of a Nāgārjuna as alchemist.

The cult of the *navanāthas* must have been popular in Āndhra, as the spiritual and material powers of these ancient masters were recalled, in public gatherings, after the fashion of the Epic and Purāṇic accounts. Writers such as Jakkana and Vallabha make allusions to this cult, as well as to general tantric practices.

In the narrative collection known as the *Bhōjarājīyamu*, the fifteenth-century Telugu author Ananta magnifies the greatness of the eleventh-century King Bhoja of Dhārā.

One of his tales brings into play the *siddha* Sarpaṭi [sic], who knew how to transmute metals with smoke: at the king's palace, he changes into gold the alloy of five metals (*pañcaloha*) with which his guest room was constructed. The king steals the secret of this alchemical operation from the credulous ascetic by promising to teach him transmutation by breath — a technique of which he did not have the slightest knowledge — in exchange. These two techniques of transmutation, with smoke (*dhūmavedha*) and breath (*śabdavedha*), are described in *Rasaśāstra*.

For Vēmana, the eminent fifteenth(?) -century poet, all knowledge is vain save for alchemy in this world, and *brahmavidyā* in the world beyond. His accounts of aurifaction, clothed in a Telugu that is as naive as it is esoteric, recalls the style of the Sanskrit alchemical treatises, especially that of the *Rasaratnākara*, attributed to the *siddha* Nityanātha. He knows of an all-purpose magical collyrium (*añjana*), and compares liberation to the transmutation of iron into gold through its contact with the philosopher's stone (*paraśa*).

According to modern historians, the main temple of Śiva Mallikārjuna was built at the heart of the Śrīśailam enclosure in either the 10th or the 13th-14th centuries. The first epigraphical reference to this holy site dates from 1063, while the most ancient known inscription found *in situ* is from 1167. Worthy of special mention is the "Pavilion of Heroes' Heads" (*Vīraśiromaṇḍapa*), built in the 14th century, at which votaries offered their heads and tongues to show their devotion to Śiva. A number of inscriptions, as well as several *prākāra* bas-reliefs, illustrate this self-sacrificial practice. These also recall the terrifying behaviour of the Śrīśailam Kāpālikas, mentioned by Bhavabhūti in his eighth-century drama *Mālatīmādhava*.

The western gateway (*paścimadvāra*) to Śrīśailam corresponds to Alampur, which was a fortified temple town under the protection of Jogulāmbā, the tutelary divinity of this *tīrtha* on the west bank of the Tuṅgabhadrā River, an *uttaravāhinī* here. Epigraphically mentioned by the name of Jogeśvarī, this "mother of yogins" is identifiable with the Yogeśvarī known to Sanskrit alchemical literature. With her terrifying features, she is considered to be a form of the horrifying Cāmuṇḍā/Caṇḍā/Caṇḍī, one of the group of Seven Mothers (*saptamātṛkā*), who were especially revered in the Cālukya age.

One also finds images of these goddesses in the sanctuary of Bāla-Brahmā, the most important of Alampur's nine temples. A local tradition relates the different compound names of these nine temples, which share the common member of Brahmeśvara (Garuḍa-, Vīra-, Padma-, Viśva-, Kumāra-, Svarga-, Tāraka-, Sūrya- [Arka-], and Bāla-Brahmeśvara), to nine plants prescribed in alchemical operations (*rasabandhamūlikās*).

The ancient main entrance to this group of shrines, which dates as far back as the seventh century, is set off by two historiated pillars, whose panels illustrate the alchemical legend of this holy place. According to the local pandit Gadiyaram Ramakrishna Sarma, who takes an unpublished *sthalapurāṇa* as his authority, these temples were built by an alchemist who had obtained the *rasa* severally from the head of Brahmeśvara, from the mouth of Jogulāmbā, from the navel of Gaṇeśa, from the toe of Pārvatī, from the right arm of Bhairava and so on. The same scholar maintains that the iconography of Alampur includes several images of *rasasiddhas*, whose alchemical practices flourished there in days gone by according to tradition. Archaeologists and epi-

graphists, however, are unable to find the slightest support for this oral and literary tradition,⁵ which, according to their evidence, is apocryphal.

Several treatises on Rasaśāstra make mention of this alchemical tradition, both at Śrīśailam and in the surrounding sacred area, which was delineated by temples that traditionally served as gateways to this celebrated holy place in Āndhra. As the unedited *Rasendramaṅgala* reminds us, Nāgārjuna Siddha took residence there to teach the practices of *rasavidyā*. The mediaeval *Ānandakanda* and *Rasaratnākara* contain long chapters on this Śaiva centre, chapters which are characterized by marvellous descriptions, which abound in recipes for the treatment of the body and for operations on metals. A favourable place for the perfect contemplatives (*siddhas*), Śrīśailam is a site which, dotted with philosophers' stones, was created by Śiva in order that his Vīraśaiva devotees might acquire supernatural powers, most especially that of *rasarasāyana* (*Vīramaheśvarāgama*).

Śrīśailam and its sacred area in Āndhra Pradesh is not the sole Indian example of a sacred geography marked by alchemical allusions and references. In fact, the descriptions of Mount Girnar in Kathiawar as well as of other Jaina pilgrimage sites exhibit a fascination with alchemy, as shown in the *Vividhatīrthakalpa*⁶ and the Jaina biographies of the alchemist and magician Nāgārjuna. This paper is thus a contribution to the study of the development of Rasaśāstra in Indian culture and is particularly related to research into the phenomenon of pilgrimage in South Asia, a theme in which Indologists have recently shown a heightened interest.⁷

⁵ See I.K. Sarma, 'Epigraphical Data on Alampur Temples and the Shrine of Jogulāmbā', *Indian Museum Bulletin* 1989 (in press). A disappointing paper: I. Sanjeeva Rao, 'Rasasiddhas of Alampur', *Bulletin of the Indian Institute of History of Medicine*, 13, 1983, 38-44.

⁶ Christine Chojnacki will give a translation of the alchemical chapter 4 on Girnar of the *Vividhatīrthakalpa*, a Jaina pilgrimage guide, in an appendix to my French paper (see *supra*).

⁷ At the University of Groningen, Professor J. Ensink initiated and supervised a research project on pilgrimage in South Asia, which enabled H. Bakker and A.W. Entwistle to compile their excellent interdisciplinary studies on Ayodhyā (1986) and Braj (1987). In the framework of the VIIth World Sanskrit Conference at Leiden in 1987, H. Bakker organized a panel on pilgrimage and edited the papers produced: *History of Sacred Places in India as reflected in Traditional Literature*, Leiden etc. 1990.

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